

THEORY OF HIGH-TEMPERATURE SUPERCONDUCTIVITY IN A TWO-LAYER SYSTEM: FeSe/SrTiO₃

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Abstract

The proposed model can qualitatively describe the occurrence of high-temperature superconductivity in FeSe/SrTiO₃. The Hamiltonian of a two-layer system is reduced to a two-band Hamiltonian, taking into account all possible pairing of electrons inside one energy band and electrons in the different energy bands. The superconductivity mechanism can be both phononic and electronic. The main factor is the presence of a large number of constants of the electron–electron interactions that contribute to the formation of Cooper pairs and also the possibility of increasing the ratio of densities of electronic energy bands N_2/N_1 by doping the systems or in some other way. A method for experimental verification of the dominance of interband interactions over intraband interactions is proposed.

1. Introduction

The discovery of high-temperature superconductivity in oxide ceramics at the end of the last century was a significant event in condensed matter physics. This discovery caused a fruitful scientific activity of experimentalists and theoreticians from different countries of the world. Activity is increased mainly in two directions: identification of the superconductivity mechanisms and the conditions leading to the occurrence of high-temperature superconductivity and the desire to design novel materials sustainable in a superconducting phase corresponding to high-temperature superconductivity. In the last decade, a large number of scientific works have been focused on the study of the properties of a class of materials represented by iron pnictides and chalcogenides. According to the studies, these materials are layered anisotropic multiband systems. A review of the recent studies of the properties of these compounds is given, for example, in [1]. In numerous compounds of this class of materials, superconductivity occurs both at low and high values of superconducting transition temperature T_c (up to 55 K). An important role in determining the superconducting properties of this class of compounds is played by the features of the electronic energy spectrum of charge carriers. These features primarily include the presence of several energy bands (electron and hole) on the Fermi surface and "nesting" conditions leading to the transition of the system in the antiferromagnetic state of the spin density wave. A violation of nesting, for example, during the doping of the system with charge carriers, contributes to the possibility of the occurrence of superconductivity.

Superconductivity can be accompanied by magnetism in a number of compounds. This fact has led to the idea of the possibility of superconductivity due to the formation of Cooper pairs and the magnetic exchange interaction of charge carriers owing to the presence of spin fluctuations.

Long-term studies have led scientists to the conclusion that most of the class of compounds under consideration obey the magnetic mechanism of superconductivity.

In superconductors in which only electron cavities or only hole cavities are observed on the Fermi surface, there are no fluctuation magnetic interactions. This fact leads to the impossibility of magnetic mechanism of superconductivity. In these systems, the main role is played by electron–electron interactions of BCS type (interband and intraband). In the case of the predominance of the interband interactions over intraband interactions, we have an interband mechanism for superconductivity [2].

The effect of overlapping of the energy bands on the Fermi surface and the various anomalies of the superconducting properties of these anisotropic systems, in principle, can be interpreted in terms of the model proposed in [3, 4]. The history of development of this direction associated with high-temperature superconductivity is given in reviews [5, 6], in several monographs and numerous papers written by M.E. Palistrant and coauthors and by other authors. The theory of multiband superconductivity requires taking into account electron–electron interactions both inside each band and between different bands of electrons [7].

Recently, much attention has been paid to studying the superconducting properties of FeSe compounds, both experimentally and theoretically [8]. This interest is mainly due to the discovery of the FeSe/SrTiO₃ structure (FeSe monolayer on a SrTiO₃ substrate) in which the superconducting transition temperature reaches record values of about 100 K. In [8], the results of a number of theoretical studies are presented, on the basis of which an attempt is made to explain this situation.

In this work, we proposed another approach to solving this problem. Main attention is paid to the mechanisms related to the structure of the FeSe/SrTiO₃ system, namely, two layers with significantly different structures (monolayer FeSe and substrate SrTiO₃), which can be considered a source of doping of the system with electrons due to oxygen deficiency in the TiO₂ layer.

The paper provides the following information:

- (i) The transition from two nonequivalent layers of the system to the band representation.
- (ii) The introduction of temperature Green functions by taking into account both the diagonal and off-diagonal approximation in the band indices.
- (iii) Derivation of a system of equations for superconducting transition temperature T_c and chemical potential μ . The self-consistency of the solution of this system by numerical methods and the representation of the dependence of T_c on the density of charge carriers \tilde{x} and magnitude μ on temperature at different values of \tilde{x} .
- (iv) Analysis and comparison of results with experimental data for FeSe/STO.

2. Transformation of the Hamiltonian and Basic Definitions

The Hamiltonian describing the state of the system is represented in the form of two nonequivalent layers. After diagonalization of the Hamiltonian and u, v -Bogolyubov transformation, the above-mentioned Hamiltonian is transformed to the band representation:

$$H = \sum_n k \sigma (\varepsilon_n(k) - \mu) a_{n k \sigma}^+ a_{n k \sigma} - \frac{1}{V} \sum_{m_1 \dots m_4} \sum_{k k'} V_{m_1 m_2}^{m_3 m_4}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}'; -\mathbf{k} \mathbf{k}') a_{m_1 k \uparrow}^+ a_{m_2 - k \downarrow}^+ a_{m_3 - k' \downarrow}^+ a_{m_4 k' \uparrow}^+, \quad (1)$$

where $a_{n k \sigma}^+$, $a_{n k \sigma}$ are the creation and annihilation operators of an electron in the n th band with

spin $\sigma = (\uparrow, \downarrow)$ and quasi-wave vector \mathbf{k} , μ is the chemical potential, and $V_{m_1 m_2}^{m_3 m_4}$ are constants of the intraband and interband interactions. This Hamiltonian is written in general terms and contains terms taking into account interactions both within each band and different interactions of electrons of different bands.

Interactions of electrons leading to the formation of Cooper pairs are determined by the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} V_{1111} &= \frac{1}{4} (V_1 + V_2 - 4J + 2Y + 4W), \\ V_{2222} &= \frac{1}{4} (V_1 + V_2 + 4J + 2Y + 4W) , \\ V_{1122} &= \frac{1}{4} (V_1 + V_2 + 4J - 2Y), \\ V_{2211} &= \frac{1}{4} (V_1 + V_2 - 4J - 2Y), \\ V_{1112} &= V_{1121} = V_{2212} = V_{2221} = V_{1211} = V_{2111} = V_{1222} = V_{2122} = \frac{V_2 - V_1}{4}, \\ V_{1212} &= V_{2121} = \frac{1}{4} (V_1 + V_2 - 2Y), \\ V_{1221} &= V_{2112} = \frac{1}{4} (V_1 + V_2 + 2Y - 4W) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\quad (3)$$

Here, V_1, V_2 are intralayer constants and Y, W are interlayer coupling constants of the electrons. On the basis of (1), simpler models can be obtained. For example, if $m_1 = m_2, m_3 = m_4$, expression (1) goes into the corresponding expression of [3], in which only intraband pairing and transition of pairs as a whole from one band to another are considered. This model is widely used for the description of superconductivity in systems with a considerable density of charge carriers ($\mu \gg T_c$), particularly high temperature. This model allows describing the anomalies of thermodynamic, magnetic, and other properties of anisotropic superconductors.

Let us consider the matrix functions \hat{G}, \hat{F} (normal and abnormal):

$$\hat{G} = \begin{pmatrix} G_{11} & G_{12} \\ G_{21} & G_{22} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \hat{F} = \begin{pmatrix} F_{11} & F_{12} \\ F_{21} & F_{22} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Using the method of Green functions [3] for Hamiltonian (1), we obtain matrix equations in the $n \vec{k} \omega$ -representation for determining the components of the Green functions (see these equations and their solutions in [7]).

In this case, for order parameters Δ_{np} , the resulting system of equations is found

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{np} = \frac{1}{\beta V} \sum_{\mathbf{k}\omega} \sum_{l,r} V_{np}^{er} F_{lr} (i\omega) &= \frac{1}{\beta V} \sum_{\mathbf{k}\omega} [V_{np}^{11} F_{11} (i\omega) + V_{np}^{22} (i\omega) + \\ &+ V_{np}^{12} F (i\omega) + V_{np}^{21} F_{21} (i\omega)] \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Let us complete system of equations (5) with the following expression:

$$x = \frac{2}{\beta V} \sum_{\mathbf{k}\omega} [G_{11} (\mathbf{k}, \omega) + G_{22} (\mathbf{k}, \omega)] e^{i\omega 0^+}, \quad (6)$$

that defines chemical potential μ . A self-consistent system of equations (5) and (6) determines order parameters Δ_{np} and chemical potential μ at a given temperature T and arbitrary values of charge carrier concentration x . For small values of the density of charge carriers x , order parameters Δ_{np} become magnitudes of the same order as chemical potentials μ ($\mu \sim \Delta_{np}$). This

feature contributes to a kink in the temperature dependence of quantity μ at the point $T = T_c$. This kink is experimentally observed in a two-band model with a low density of charge carriers and should manifest itself more clearly than in the single-band model [10] due to the presence of several order parameters (Δ_{mn}).

Fig. 1. Dependence of T_c on the density of charge carriers \tilde{x} (see the text for the meaning of the parameters).

Fig.2. Temperature dependence of chemical potential μ for different concentrations of charge carriers x . Curves 1, 2, and 3 correspond to $\tilde{x} = x/2N_1 = 0.015, 0.02,$ and $0.03,$ respectively.

3. Superconducting Transition Temperature and Chemical Potential

Let us consider the above-mentioned equations (5) and (6) at a temperature close to the superconducting transition temperature ($T \sim T_c$). With this purpose, we perform the following:

(i) Expand with respect to the product of small parameters $\Delta_{nm}\Delta_{mn}$ in (5), (6) and restrict ourselves to linear terms of the expansion parameters ($n; m = 1, 2$).

(ii) Present the temperature dependence of order parameter Δ_{nm} as follows:

$$\Delta_{nm} = c_{nm} (\beta - \beta_c)^{1/2} + c_{nm}^{(1)} (\beta - \beta_c)^{3/2} + \dots$$

(iii) Based on these operations, the resulting self-consistent system of equations is obtained for superconducting transition temperature T_c and chemical potential μ .

(iv) Perform the summation over Matsubara frequency ω by the usual method adopted in statistical physics.

(v) Obtain only electronic energy bands on the Fermi surface, define the dispersion law for each energy band, and switch from summation over momentum \mathbf{k} to integration over energy in accordance with the introduced energy law of the dispersion of the electron.

(vi) Input a pseudo-band index by the following rule

$$11 \rightarrow 1', 22 \rightarrow 2', 12 \rightarrow 3', 21 \rightarrow 4'$$

and notations

$$V_{nmpl} \rightarrow U_{n'm'}, \quad \text{where } n'; m' = 1 - 4. \quad (7)$$

We obtain the following system of equations for coefficients c_n :

$$c_{n'} = - \frac{\Sigma}{m'} N_{m'} J_{m'} U_{n'm'} c_{m'}. \quad (8)$$

Equating the determinant of this system to zero, we obtain the equation for determining the superconducting transition temperature. In (8) $N_n J_n$ ($n = 1 \dots 4$) is the expression that depends on T_c and other parameters of the theory (for details, see [7]). The obtained system of equations for Δ_{nm} and for μ did not supply analytical consideration and can be solved by numerical methods.

Figure 1 presents the dependence of the superconducting transition temperature T_c on the concentration of charge carriers $\tilde{x} = \frac{x}{2} N_1$. In this figure, curve 1 corresponds to values of the ratio of the density of electronic states of the two energy bands $N_2/N_1 = 1$ and the effective constants of electron interaction $\lambda_{11} = \lambda_{22} = 0,2, \lambda_{34} = \lambda_{43} = 0.105; \lambda_{12} = \lambda_{21} = \lambda_{33} = \lambda_{44} = 0.01$; other λ_{nm} ($n, m = 1-4$). Curve 2 describes the case in which $N_2/N_1 = 1$ and the following values of parameters λ_{nm} : $\lambda_{11} = \lambda_{22} = 0.2; \lambda_{21} = \lambda_{12} = \lambda_{33} = \lambda_{44} = 0.1; \lambda_{34} = \lambda_{43} = 0.15$; the rest $\lambda_{nm} = 0.01$. For curve 3, we have $N_2/N_1 = 0.5$; λ_{nm} values are the same as for curve 2.

Figure 2 shows the dependence of chemical potential μ on temperature T . In this figure, a kink is observed at the point of $T = T_c$. This result is attributed to the low density of states x in the given system due to the emergence of order parameters Δ_{nm} at $T < T_c$ which are the magnitudes of the order of chemical potential μ . Thus, this anomaly is observed both in single-band discharged systems and in the presence of several energy bands on the Fermi surface. In this paper, numerical studies were performed by self-consistent consideration of equations (5) and (6), after many analytical transformations mentioned above, and ultimately led to an equation for T_c , for example, equation (8).

4. Main Results and Conclusions

In this paper, we have developed a theory of superconductivity of a layered system consisting of two nonequivalent layers with an arbitrary density of charge carriers, including a small one ($\mu \sim T_c$).

The problem has been solved in the case of a discharged system, assuming the occurrence of superconductivity in the BCS scenario, i.e., by the formation of Cooper pairs of electrons.

The method of transition to the band representation and the method of Green's functions in the nondiagonal approximation that contributes to the identification of the role of additional order parameters Δ_{nm} ($n; m = 1..4$) has been developed and applied.

The model essentially contains a transition to a pseudo-band representation of four bands. Under these conditions, all interband and intraband pairing of charge carriers are taken into account.

The main results are as follows:

(i) Hamiltonian of a bilayer system with unequal layers has been introduced; the transition to the band representation has been performed. The transformed Hamiltonian takes into account all sorts of both intraband and interband electron–electron interactions leading to the appearance of Cooper pairs within each band and between electrons of different bands. The obtained self-consistent system of equations for determining the superconducting transition temperature T_c (5) and chemical potential μ (6) is presented in the four-band model representation.

(ii) Numerical simulations have been performed; it has been shown that, for discharged systems, it is possible to obtain high T_c values because of the additional interband interactions associated with the formation of superconducting pairs of electrons of the different bands.

(iii) This model has also a great opportunity for various multi-layered or multi-band systems because a substantial role in the theory is played by the N_2/N_1 ratio of the electronic densities of the different bands.

(iv) The solution in Fig. 1 clearly shows the above-mentioned results. The effect of the additional interactions is shown in curves 1 and 3; the essential role of the N_2/N_1 ratio follows from comparison of curves 3 and 4.

(v) The temperature dependence of the magnitude of μ , in the region of low densities of charge carriers, exhibits a kink (curves 1–3), which becomes less sharp with increasing charge carrier concentration and vanishes in the case of the single-band model of a superconductor at $\mu = 2$ meV in [8] and in two-band models for $\mu \sim 8$ meV (Fig. 2). It should be noted that the existence of additional constants of the electron–electron interaction in a double-layered system leads to a stronger manifestation of this anomaly, which can be detected experimentally. Thus, it is possible to confirm the presence of a fairly strong interband electron–electron interaction in nonequivalent double-layered superconducting structures, which are important factors in the emergence of high-temperature superconductivity.

(vi) The structure of the considered double-layered structure is equivalent to the FeSe/SrTiO₃ system. The physical properties and anomalies of this structure qualitatively describe the properties of the FeSe/SrTiO₃ structure [8]. This statement holds true for both phonon and non phonon mechanisms of superconductivity in a discharged system, such as FeSe/SrTiO₃. It is necessary to have high values of the electron–electron interaction constants and the possibility of changing the ratio of electronic densities N_2/N_1 .

References

- [1] A.Y. Chubukov and P.J. Hirschfeld, Phys. Today 68, 46 (1915). arXiv: 14171.
- [2] M.E. Palistrant, Zh. Eksp. Teor. Fiz. 150 (1), 97 (2016).
- [3] V.A. Moskalenko, Fiz. Met. Metalloved. 8, 503 (1959).
- [4] H. Suhl, B.T. Matthias, and L.R. Wolker, Phys Rev. Lett. 3, 552 (1959).
- [5] M.E. Palistrant, Cond. Mat. Phys. 12, 677 (2009); Mold. J. Phys. Sci. 3, 133 (2004). arXiv: cond-mat/0305496.
- [6] V.A. Moskalenko, M. E. Palistrant, and V. M. Vakalyuk, Usp. Fiz. Nauk 161, 155 (1991).

- [7] F.G. Kochorbe and M. E. Palistrant, Zh. Eksp. Teor. Fiz. 104, 3084 (1993).
- [8] M.V. Sadvskii, Usp. Fiz. Nauk 186 (10), 1035 (2016).
- [9] A.A. Abrikosov, L.P. Gorkov, and I.E. Dzyaloshinski, Metody kvantovoi teorii polya v statisticheskoi fizike, Moscow, Fizmatgiz, 1962.
- [10] D. Van Der Marel, Physica C 165, 35 (1965).